
Religious Transgression in Nadine Gordimer's *The Pickup*

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Nadine Gordimer's *The Pickup* (2001) is a piece of post-apartheid 'literature of transition', taking as its subject-matter the issues of inter-racial love, displacement, coloured, and migration. Appeared in the first year of the new millennium, the novel won the 2002 Commonwealth Writers' Prize for the Best Book from Africa – in addition to having been included on the final 24 Booker Prize 'longlist' for 2001. *The Pickup* deals with immigration and a white woman's adaptability in an Arab background. The novel is centred upon the Middle East. Having been cut off from the rest of the world and, particularly, from the rest of Africa for so long under apartheid, the new South Africa opened its borders to a wide range of peoples, many of them settling as 'illegal immigrants' in the big cities like Johannesburg. This has given rise to reactions of xenophobia and resentment among local people, despite the fact that, as Gordimer has pointed out, "apart from South African Africans themselves ... we are all immigrants here." So In post-apartheid South Africa, Gordimer turned to other global issues. However, the white Western journalists expected her to provide the details of the condition of whites in South Africa. Protesting against such indirect censorship, Gordimer asks, "What kind of fossil should I be, unearthed from

the cave of bones that was apartheid, if my essential sense of self were to be as a white?" (Gordimer 1999)

Amos Oz described *The Pickup* as a modern Romeo and Juliet story. However, in 'a Pickup interview', Gordimer told to the German *Welt am Sonntag* that the novel is anything but a romanticisation of immigrant striving.' (Gordimer 2002) For critics like Sarah Nuttall, xenophobia in the post-apartheid society in South Africa is an immediate consequence of the failure of the liberation movement to breed 'a Pan-African Consciousness.' (Nuttall 2004) Thus the issue of displacement is both an age-old and recent one that lies at the heart of a South African sense of belonging. (Kossew 2005)

The novel recounts the story of two characters whose social origins are poles apart: Julie Summers, a white, working woman and Abdu, an Arab immigrant living illegally in South Africa. (Not until page 109 is his full name disclosed as Ibrahim ibn Musa.) The novel is partly set in post-liberation South Africa (up to p.108) and partly in an unnamed Arab country (109-268). The novel is, in many ways, an extended version of Gordimer's 1981 novel *July's People*. Maureen in *July's People* tries to maintain her identity as a ruler while she is a refugee to her black servant whereas Julie Summers in *The Pickup* attempts to

merge herself in a deserted village of a coloured lover. Gordimer is fascinated by the kinds of power shifts that occur when people become displaced from their comfort zones, a theme she has, of course, already minutely explored in *July's People*, and has to adapt to new ways of thinking and being. Abdu, twenty-eight, one year younger than Julie, is from a country in the Middle East partitioned by colonial powers on their departure. It is one of those countries where one "can't tell religion apart from politics, their form of persecution from the persecution of poverty, as the reason for getting out and going wherever they will let you in" (12). Abdu is himself a desperate global roamer, 'a grease monkey': an untrained engineer who must work as an au. Abdu hates his own country for its religious and political factions, corrupt government, religious oppression, cross-border conflict, no work, no development (14). Gordimer, here presents the bleak reality in almost all newly liberated countries in the Middle East and Asia. Ronald Suresh Roberts opines that Gordimer's portrayal of Abdu lacks the fierce unsentimental intelligence that graced such characters earlier in her writing life. When it is clear that Ibrahim should leave the country, they prepare for the departure. Julie undertakes the domestic task while generally people like her have a black woman who comes to clean and wash and iron (61). It's through William Plomer's poem that Gordimer reveals Julie's psychological preparation to leave South Africa for Ibrahim's country:

Let us go to another country
Not yours or mine
And start again (88) - William
Plomer (*Collected Poems*, 1973)

Julie is preparing herself for a new adventure in her life, to migrate to a country 'without fires, where hope would be their passport' (89). Ibrahim seems very close to her while 'her crowd, Mates, Brothers and

Sisters, the strangers.' The members at The Table are also disturbed due to the restlessness of Julie and Ibrahim. Obviously, their chief concern is for Julie. One of them remarks distastefully: "This pick up (Ibrahim) of hers's been a disaster from the beginning." Another defends him saying: "Come on, he's not a bad guy, he just needs a meal ticket. A bed. And he obviously knew how to occupy it" (92). Ibrahim is shocked to know that Julie is going to accompany him to his own country. For him, the decision is nothing but 'a madness. Stupidity.' He knows at his heart that she is not for him. His country would prove a hell for her and her kind- the whites. She couldn't go out alone in that 'run-down depraved strip of a country Europeans didn't even want to hold on to any longer, were glad to get rid of, even the oil is over the border.' it is to live there, you can wish you were dead, if you have to live there. Can't you understand? I can't be for you-responsible." (95) The hatred for the countries and the culture of the Middle East is revealed through Nigel Ackroyd Summers. The miserable condition of women, poor condition of health facilities and the disgusting interference of religion into the day-to-day life has been the chief objections of the White Western world towards the Middle East, which is, unfortunately the fact.

However, Julie doesn't change her mind and leaves the country with Ibrahim. She crosses the thick wall of racial and religious extremes between her and Abdu and bridges the cultural gap for herself. It is undoubtedly a revolutionary decision for a privileged white like Julie. The cottage, for her, was 'a doll's house' while the EL-AY Café a game that she was playing with reality. (164) The desert has two different meanings for Julie and Ibrahim. For Julie, it's an 'eternity, a space with 'no measure of space ... no demarcation from land to air' (172) while to Ibrahim, it's nothing but 'a

dusty hell' (173). Julie feels a strange kind of self-consciousness in Ibrahim's country. She is strange to the people and also to herself. There, in South Africa, she was a working, white, bourgeois woman whereas in Ibrahim's land she is looked upon just as Abdu's wife, nothing else. She feels lost. (Gerdin 2006) In spite of her urban and individualist background, Julie does her best to fit herself into the culture of Ibrahim's home-land. She even keeps fast during the month of Ramadan. However, she is looked upon as a stranger. Even the children run away from her when she laughs and holds her arms wide to receive them (119). This failure of cultural expedition of Julie is expressed through the lines from the Koran:

He hath let loose the two seas which meet each other

Yet between them is a barrier which they overpass not

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